

TECHNIQUES AND METHODS USED IN MOTHER TONGUE TEACHING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8058554>

Abstract: This article talks about the techniques and methods used in teaching the mother tongue. Methods of preparation of targeted instructions have a great impact on the independence and social development of students. These techniques can be successfully implemented in many activities.

Keywords: problem-based learning methods, independent generation of concepts, sales environment, exercises, manuals and training materials.

There are many techniques and methods used in mother tongue teaching. Among them, the following are of great importance:

1. Problem-based learning methods - This method combines several learning methods and topics to improve the quality of learning for students. This method develops students' understanding through activities such as practical exercises and two-way dialogues.
2. Independent generation of concepts - In this method, the teacher requires students to think independently and increase the concepts that have arisen in order to answer questions. This method helps students to express their thoughts even when questions arise.
3. Refrigeration Environment - This method is a kind of digital war program that aims to present the available educational materials to the students. In this method, students learn a variety of combat materials such as computer, text, pictures, and videos.
4. Exercises - help students learn through practical exercises. Use of modern equipment and tools, service and management of motor vehicles, etc. flavors are used in many work processes such as
5. Manuals and Study Materials - There are many manuals and study materials available for students to master. Through these materials, students can get answers to expected questions and other information related to the syllabus.
6. Analysis and review: The teacher is one of the main techniques for students to be able to analyze and review and to organize this process. When using these techniques, you should pay more attention to students' understanding and interpretation of the questions.
7. Pointing: In external tasks or tests, the teacher is giving instructions to the students by pointing. In order to be able to guide, teachers need to have a good understanding of concepts such as reviewing students' reading books, models, diagnoses, etc.
8. Teaching languages used in other languages of Uzbekistan: English and Russian are often taught in secondary and higher education in Uzbekistan. Knowledge of these languages is essential for students and explains the teacher's intended purpose in using them correctly.
9. Link to Candy-Employment: How to help teachers create easy-to-use links for students and access them using links to links to Candy-Employment.

10. Use of Multimedia: Use of multimedia is the use of media such as large videos, images, etc. designed to illustrate student concepts.

11. Games: Incorporating games into a teacher's lesson can help students master the learning process. Games can be used to improve motivation, increase the number of concepts and questions, and restore information with the help of instructions.

12. Interactive application: Through the use of interactive technology, students have come up with tests to change and improve. The teacher can organize tests for a large group to demonstrate or apply their skills and talents during future paper work.

13. Manuals are the main tools of teaching, in which detailed instructions are given about the knowledge of students. Students read manuals to increase their knowledge.

The above methods can be used in accordance with each other or in combination. These techniques and methods enhance student learning and reinforce the learning process.

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